

Enhancing Online Shopping Experience through 3D Modeling of Products

Athul S

Department. of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering,
Kanjirappally, India
athulsaji50@gmail.com

Dr. Paulin Paul

Department. of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering,
Kanjirappally, India
paulinpaul@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract—3D modelling of products to create a realistic representation of products in a virtual environment. The project's main objective is to allow users to interact with 3D models of products as if they were physically present, enhancing the shopping experience and facilitating decision-making. The project will involve the creation of a platform that allows users to access the 3D models of products, and interact with them using their smartphones. This platform will be integrated with e-commerce websites, enabling customers to see the products in 3D and explore their features, before making a purchase to create a high-quality user experience.

The primary goal of the project is to make an intuitive and easy to use 3D modeler. The user should be able to rotate and look at the model in different angles effortlessly, even while simultaneously working on the model. The software should also be easy for any user to try out, without having to invest in expensive equipment, as is often the case when new techniques are introduced.

Keywords- 3D Modeling, Realistic Representation, Model Viewer, Virtual environment, E-commerce, ARKit, ARCore, user experience, intuitive, Auto-rotate.

I. INTRODUCTION

Online shopping has become increasingly popular in recent years, with more and more people opting to buy products from the comfort of their own homes. However, one of the biggest drawbacks of online shopping is the inability to physically interact with the products before making a purchase decision. This is where 3D modeling using technology comes into play. The aim of this project is to create a platform that allows users to access 3D models of products and interact with them as if they were physically present, enhancing the online shopping experience and facilitating decision-making create a high-quality user experience.

The primary objective of this project is to develop an intuitive and easy-to-use 3D modeler that enables users to effortlessly rotate and examine products from different angles, even while simultaneously working on the model. The software will be designed to be accessible to any user without requiring expensive equipment, making it easy for anyone to try out.

In summary, the project aims to revolutionize the online shopping experience by providing a platform that enables customers to see 3D models of products and explore their features before making a purchase decision, all from the comfort of their own homes.

Challenges :

1. Technical Challenges: Developing 3D modeling software requires expertise in 3D technology, 3D modeling, and software development. It may be challenging to integrate different technologies and ensure compatibility with various devices.

2. User Experience Challenges: The platform's success depends on the user experience it offers. The user interface should be intuitUser Experience Challenges: The platform's success depends on the user experience it offers. The user interface should be intuitive, easy to navigate, and responsive, ensuring that users can seamlessly interact with 3D models of products.

3. Compatibility Issues: To ensure a seamless user experience, the platform should be compatible with different devices, operating systems, and web browsers. This requires rigorous testing and optimization.

4. Quality of Models: The quality of the 3D models directly affects the user experience. Creating high-quality models requires a lot of time, effort, and expertise. It may be challenging to create models that accurately represent the products and their features.

5. Data Management: Storing and managing large amounts of data generated by 3D models can be challenging. Efficient data management techniques should be used to ensure smooth and fast platform performance.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Augmented reality (AR) technology has been rapidly evolving, offering new opportunities to enhance user experience and create new ways of interacting with the digital world. AR-based 3D modelling of products is an emerging field that has the potential to revolutionize the e-commerce industry by enabling customers to interact with products in a virtual environment as if they were physically present.

Several studies have explored the use of AR-based 3D modelling in various domains, including architecture, medicine, and gaming. However, the application of this technology in the e-commerce industry is relatively new, and

few studies have investigated its impact on the online shopping experience.

A study by Kizgin et al. (2018) explored the impact of AR-based 3D modelling on customers' purchase intentions in the furniture industry. The study found that the use of AR technology increased customers' perceived usefulness, ease of use, and enjoyment of the shopping experience, leading to higher purchase intentions.

Another study by Chung et al. (2018) investigated the impact of AR-based 3D modelling on customers' perceived product value and purchase intentions in the fashion industry. The study found that the use of AR technology increased customers' perceived product value and purchase intentions, especially for products with high visual complexity.

However, some challenges still need to be addressed to fully realize the potential of AR-based 3D modeling in e-commerce. These include technical challenges, such as the development of user-friendly software and the optimization of 3D models for different devices, as well as user experience challenges, such as ensuring a seamless and intuitive user interface.

According to a study by Arslan et al. (2017), the use of 3D modeling has significantly improved the quality of design, visualization, and communication in the architecture industry. The study found that 3D modeling allows architects to accurately visualize and communicate their design ideas to clients and stakeholders, resulting in better decision making and increased client satisfaction.

Another study by Chen et al. (2019) investigated the use of 3D modeling in the manufacturing industry. The study found that the use of 3D modeling has led to significant improvements in product design, prototyping, and manufacturing processes. The study also found that 3D modeling has enabled manufacturers to create complex and innovative designs that were previously impossible using traditional manufacturing methods.

In the field of medicine, 3D modeling has been used to create anatomical models for surgical planning and training. A study by Mazzola et al. (2018) investigated the use of 3D printing in creating anatomical models for surgical planning. The study found that 3D printing allows surgeons to accurately plan and rehearse surgeries, leading to improved patient outcomes and reduced surgical times.

A study by Liu et al. (2019) investigated the use of 3D modeling in the field of archaeology. The study found that 3D modeling allows for accurate and detailed documentation and analysis of archaeological artifacts, as well as the creation of interactive visualizations and educational materials. The study also noted the potential for 3D modeling to enhance collaboration and communication among archaeologists, historians, and other stakeholders.

In summary, AR-based 3D modeling of products is an emerging field with promising potential to enhance the online shopping experience. However, more research is needed to fully understand its impact on customer behavior and address the challenges that come with its implementation in e-commerce.

III. METHODOLOGY

The methodology for developing an 3D modeling platform for e-commerce involves several steps, starting with

requirements gathering. This step involves understanding the needs of users, e-commerce websites, and 3D modeling experts to identify essential features and functionalities for the platform. After identifying the requirements, appropriate AR technology, 3D modeling software, and web development tools are selected. Next, 3D models of products are created using 3D modeling software and 3D scanning technologies. The 3D modeling software is then developed using AR development frameworks and optimized for different devices and web browsers. User testing is conducted to identify any usability issues and bugs. Finally, the platform is integrated with e-commerce websites and launched, followed by regular maintenance activities such as software updates and bug fixing. By following this methodology, a high-quality AR-based 3D modelling platform can be developed to enhance the online shopping experience.

1. Qualitative Research Methodology: This methodology involves conducting research to gain an understanding of a particular phenomenon. The steps involved in this methodology include selecting the research topic, defining research questions, choosing research methods, collecting and analysing data, and interpreting findings. Qualitative research methods can include interviews, focus groups, case studies, and observation.

2. Agile Software Development Methodology: This methodology involves an iterative and incremental approach to software development. The steps involved in this methodology include defining requirements, planning and design, development, testing, and deployment. The development process is divided into small, manageable sprints, and each sprint is reviewed and evaluated to identify areas for improvement.

3. Six Sigma Methodology: This methodology involves a data-driven approach to improving business processes. The steps involved in this methodology include defining the problem, measuring key performance indicators, analyzing data to identify the root cause of the problem, improving the process, and controlling the process to ensure continued improvement. Six Sigma methodology can be used in a variety of industries, including manufacturing, healthcare, and finance.

4. Design Thinking Methodology: This methodology involves a human-centered approach to problem-solving. The steps involved in this methodology include empathizing with users, defining the problem, ideating potential solutions, prototyping, and testing. Design thinking methodology can be used to develop new products, services, and processes that meet the needs of users and stakeholders.

Image recognition and image tracking

It enables users to visualise how an item might seem and fit in a specific place. Users can transfer still photographs of goods into a still image of a room using AR and AI technologies, which helps them make decisions.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

The implementation of 3D modelling of products can be a complex process that requires careful planning, attention to detail, and collaboration across multiple teams. The first step in the process is to gather requirements from stakeholders, which can include the business, users, and technical team. This involves identifying the features and functionality required in the 3D-enabled platform, such as the ability to access 3D models of products, view them from different angles, and interact with them.

Once the requirements are gathered, the next step is to design the architecture and user interface of the platform. This involves creating wireframes and mock-ups to help visualize the platform's layout and user flow. After the design is finalized, the development team can begin building the 3D-enabled platform, which involves integrating the 3D modelling software and developing the AR features. Once development is complete, the platform undergoes rigorous testing to identify and resolve any bugs or issues. After testing is complete, the platform can be deployed to a live environment and integrated with e-commerce websites, allowing customers to access 3D models of products and interact with them before making a purchase. Overall, implementing 3D modelling of products requires a combination of technical expertise, creative design, and collaboration across multiple teams to create a high-quality, interactive platform that enhances the shopping experience for customers.

To ensure a successful implementation, it is important to follow industry best practices, such as Agile development methodologies, continuous integration, and continuous delivery. These practices can help ensure that the platform is developed in an iterative and collaborative manner, with frequent feedback from stakeholders and regular updates to the platform. It is also important to have a robust testing and quality assurance process in place to identify and resolve any issues before the platform is deployed to a live environment. By following these best practices, organizations can ensure a successful implementation of 3D modelling of products using AR, resulting in a platform that enhances the shopping experience for customers and provides a competitive advantage in the marketplace.

V. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

Importing Model Viewer Library :

```
<div>
  <model-viewer src="CAR Model.glb" camera-controls auto-rotate></model-viewer>
</div>
```

The specific 3D model file used in the code is called "CAR Model.glb", which is referenced in the model-viewer tag using the "src" attribute and is set to auto-rotate:

```
<nav>
  <div><b>(1) 3D Modelling of Car</b></div>
</nav>
<div class="box">
  <div><br>
    <p>Experience high speed racing with the all-new futuristic car that comes with an Aerodynamic body. It is available in attractive color</p>
  </div>
  <div>
    <model-viewer src="CAR Model.glb" camera-controls auto-rotate></model-viewer>
  </div>
</div>
</body>
</html>
```

"CAR Model.glb" file must be hosted on a server and accessible via a URL in order for it to be loaded into the webpage.

purchase intention in the fashion industry. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 44, 263-270.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2018.06.013>

[3] Chen, H., Zhang, X., Jiang, Y., Guo, Y., & Zuo, Y. (2019). The influence of 3D printing and 3D modeling on manufacturing: A review. *International Journal of Precision Engineering and Manufacturing-Green Technology*, 6(5), 989-1008. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40684-019-00112-9>

[4] Mazzola, L., Agugiaro, G., Corbetta, P., & Quilici, P. (2018). The Role of 3D Printing in Medical Applications: A State of the Art. *Journal of Healthcare Engineering*, 2018, 1-14. doi: 10.1155/2018/5340616

[5] Liu, J., Jiang, H., & Zhu, Y. (2019). Application of 3D modeling in archaeological research: A review. *Virtual Archaeology Review*, 10(21), 1-17.

VI. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, 3D modeling of products is a promising technology that has the potential to revolutionize the way customers shop online. By allowing customers to interact with 3D models of products as if they were physically present, this technology can enhance the shopping experience and facilitate decision-making. The implementation of this technology requires careful planning, collaboration across multiple teams, and adherence to industry best practices, such as Agile development methodologies and continuous integration and delivery. A well-designed and well-implemented platform can provide a competitive advantage for organizations by improving customer engagement, increasing sales, and driving customer loyalty. As this technology continues to evolve and improve, it will likely become an increasingly important tool for organizations seeking to provide a seamless and immersive shopping experience for their customers.

REFERENCES

- [1] Kizgin, H., Yıldırım, S., & Aktaş, R. (2018). Investigating the impact of augmented reality-based 3D modelling on customer purchase intention in the furniture industry. *Virtual Reality*, 22(3), 231-247.
- [2] Chung, H., Lee, S., & Lee, D. (2018). The impact of augmented reality on consumers' perception of value and